

Evolving Educational Paradigms: Soft Skills Integration in South African Accounting Programs

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Given that integrating soft skills assessments into accounting curricula is crucial for preparing professionals for the Fourth Industrial Revolution (4IR) challenges. This study contributes to the literature by exploring the development and assessment of soft skills within the South African Institute of Chartered Accountants (SAICA)-Accredited programmes in South African Higher Education Institutions (HEIs). In doing so, the study offers insights into the evolving landscape of education and its alignment with the demands of the 4IR. Through a rigorous, non-systematic qualitative research approach that ensures validity and reliability, this study revised a sample of 14 carefully selected peer-reviewed journal articles to investigate methods used by SAICA-accredited programmes to assess soft skills. The study found that studies examining soft skills in the context of the 4IR commonly lack detailed insights into soft skills assessment methods in SAICA-accredited accounting programs. This necessitates future studies to be explicit on the methods used to assess soft skills to benefit academics. Drawing from knowledge gaps identified in the literature, and personal experiences of teaching on accountancy modules in HEIs within South Africa, the researchers, proposes assessment adaptations and actions, including contextual alignment, assessment design, validity and reliability, feedback and development, ethical considerations, and continuous improvement.

Keywords: Soft skills, SAICA, 4IR, assessment, accountancy, South Africa

For the past twenty years, the quality of accounting education has faced considerable examination. This scrutiny stems from substantial shifts in the professional environment for accountants (Pasewark, 2021; Rinaldi, 2022). Although a body of research consistently highlights that accountancy graduates must possess industry-relevant skills and competencies (Plant, Barac, & Sarens, 2019; Tsigiris & Bowyer, 2021) a disconnect persists between the learning outcomes of higher education and the actual demands of employers. Prioritising the specific soft skills crucial for success in the accounting field presents a viable strategy for bridging this gap. In fact, the misalignment is reported for soft skills, and not in technical and professional ethics. In the 4IR era, accounting courses prioritize soft skills, that is, communication, critical thinking, decision-making, problem-solving, adaptability, emotional intelligence, leadership and teamwork (Moyo & Kanyane, 2024) adaptability. These are essential alongside technical expertise, enabling effective collaboration, innovation, and resilience in automation-driven roles. In reality, soft skills such as communication, critical thinking, adaptability, collaboration, and

creativity are vital for accounting graduates. Communication ensures effective interaction with clients and colleagues (Papageorgiou & Callaghan, 2020). Critical thinking helps analyse complex financial data (Plant et al., 2019). Adaptability allows for flexibility in rapidly changing environments (Mabe & Bwalya, 2022). Collaboration fosters teamwork, while creativity drives innovation in problem-solving (Landsberg & van den Berg, 2023). In developed nations like Australia, the United States, Canada, and the United Kingdom, the evaluation of soft skills within accounting degrees commonly relies on a blended approach, measuring both individual and collaborative performance (Das & Singh, 2018). Standard assessment techniques in these contexts encompass class participation, presentations, group projects, case studies, written assignments, internships, and behavioural assessments (Rebele & Pierre, 2019).

The situation in emerging economies, however, reveals a more nuanced picture. While many of the same methods are employed, their application is often adapted to local educational contexts and resource constraints (Hunter, Lee, & Massey, 2023; Rebele & Pierre, 2019). The literature identifies prevalent assessment tools in these regions, including oral presentations, case studies, role-playing simulations, collaborative projects, and practical training, often with a pronounced emphasis on ethics and dedicated soft skills workshops (Das & Singh, 2018). It is crucial to recognise that the specific mix and implementation of these approaches are not uniform; they are shaped by an institution's resources, the cultural setting, and the national education framework (Lauder & Mayhew, 2020). Despite these variations, the overarching goal remains consistent: to equip accounting graduates in emerging economies with the essential soft skills required for professional success and to navigate an increasingly dynamic global business landscape.

Within the South African context, undergraduate accounting programmes employ a range of assessment techniques designed to

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We have no known conflict of interest to disclose.

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evaluate soft skills through both individual and collaborative tasks (Lansdell, Mohammadali-Haji, & Marx, 2020). According to the literature, common practices involve class participation, presentations, group projects, written assignments, and case studies. This is often supplemented by internships, work-integrated learning placements, dedicated professional skills programmes, and various forms of behavioural assessment (Landsberg & van den Berg, 2023). Naturally, the precise mix of these methods differs from one university to another, with each institution potentially adopting further approaches tailored to its unique curriculum and objectives. Ultimately, these varied forms of assessment are instrumental in cultivating the specific soft skills graduates require to excel in the South African accounting profession.

Although the accounting profession widely acknowledges that graduates must acquire soft skills (Papageorgiou & Callaghan, 2020), South African higher education lacks a standardised framework for effectively evaluating these competencies. This research identified the specific gap in soft skills assessment through a comprehensive process, which included a systematic literature review, a critical evaluation of prevailing assessment techniques, an analysis of practical implementation challenges, consultations with key stakeholders, and a comparative study of successful international models. These findings underscore the urgent need for a cohesive framework to guide the assessment of soft skills within the accounting discipline, a necessity also highlighted by recent scholars (Alshbili & Elamer, 2020; Dolce, Emanuel, Cisi, & Ghislieri, 2020; Getahun & Mersha, 2020).

Although the teaching and assessment of technical, ethical, and digital skills in accounting are well-established in the literature (Cimatti, 2016) the same level of scrutiny has not been applied to the methods used for assessing soft skills. The significance of these skills for accountants is not in dispute (Landsberg & van den Berg, 2023; Stuebs et al., 2023) however, a clear research gap exists regarding how they are cultivated and evaluated within South African accounting programmes, and the overall effectiveness of these approaches. This paper, therefore, seeks to investigate how concepts of the 4IR era are integrated and aligned with the established methods for developing and assessing soft skills in SAICA-accredited programmes at South African universities. The research focuses on the interaction of the SAICA competency framework with 4IR trends, exploring their combined impact on professional development. This focus is vital for navigating the shifting demands of the accounting profession. By analysing the incorporation of 4IR principles into SAICA-accredited curricula, the study promotes a crucial alignment between the evolving needs of the industry and the outputs of higher education, ultimately enhancing graduate preparedness for a technology-centric professional environment.

The 4IR Era Technologies

The contemporary professional landscape is characterised by profound shifts, including globalisation, intensified competition on both domestic and international fronts, and the swift progression of digital and communication technologies. Within accounting education, the 4IR technologies are fundamentally transforming pedagogy through the incorporation of automation, data analytics, and artificial intelligence (Landsberg & van den Berg, 2023). This shift is restructuring curricula to prioritise digital competence, analytical reasoning, and adaptability, thereby equipping students for

the changing demands of data-centric decision-making and innovative accounting practice in an era of continuous technological change.

Previous studies by Menon and Castrillón (2019) indicate that for higher education to effectively prepare students for the challenges of the 4IR era, it must embrace flexible curricula and teaching methodologies adaptable to varied contexts. These scholars argue that this new era demands a fundamental rethinking of how 'skills' are conceptualised and evaluated. They call for innovative assessment strategies for soft skills that align with the fluid demands of a technology-intensive world, a shift they deem critical for success in 4IR-driven workplaces. Further reinforcing this, the literature underscores the necessity for innovative curriculum design to create an empowering pedagogy for the 4IR (Menon & Castrillón, 2019; Chaka, 2020). A significant obstacle, however, is that while the need for curriculum transformation is acknowledged, a prevailing reliance on rigid, predefined categories continues to hinder the development of curricula that meet these new imperatives. This highlights an urgent need to assess 4IR soft skills more effectively. Echoing this sentiment, Mabe and Bwalya (2022) assert that soft skills are increasingly pivotal for unlocking the potential of the 4IR. Their research within the South African context found that participants perceived soft skills as holding greater significance than hard technical skills.

Scholars have consistently documented the evolving competencies demanded of graduates in a technology-driven workplace (Hattingh, 2018; Halili, Fathima, & Razak, 2022; Potokri, 2022). Despite this awareness, a significant shortfall persists in the research concerning effective methods for assessing the necessary soft skills within this new context. The South African Institute of Chartered Accountants (SAICA) developed a competency framework to outline these essential graduate attributes and to steer universities in updating their curricula. Nevertheless, the practical effectiveness of this framework remains an open question. A systematic review conducted by Landsberg and van den Berg (2023) offers a valuable analysis of how accountancy programme module documents at leading South African universities are responding to 4IR workforce requirements. Their findings indicate that while skills related to business acumen receive sufficient attention, competencies in digital, relational, and decision-making acumen are notably under-addressed. Addressing business acumen skills involves understanding financial concepts and industry dynamics. Digital acumen skills pertain to proficiency in technology, data analysis, and digital tools. Relational acumen skills focus on effective communication, collaboration, and interpersonal relationships. Decision-making acumen skills entail critical thinking, problem-solving, and strategic decision-making abilities (Klein et al., 2019). Together, they form a holistic framework for navigating complex business environments. This study, therefore, questions whether current curricula are adequately preparing students for the 4IR workforce. It underscores the necessity for further investigation into robust soft skills assessment methods and the practical, effective implementation of the SAICA 2025 competency framework.

The Teaching and Assessment of Soft Skills in an Academic Programme

Senior managers frequently observe that new graduates, while technically knowledgeable, often lack the essential soft skills required for workplace success, noting that proficient communication is a decisive factor in achieving positive outcomes (Barac & Moloi, 2020; Kavanagh & Drennan, 2008; Tan et al.,

2022). This feedback confirms that to thrive in today's volatile business landscape, accountants require a balanced combination of technical expertise and non-technical abilities like communication, problem-solving, and critical thinking (Landsberg & van den Berg, 2023; Stuebs et al., 2023). Consequently, accounting education programmes must integrate training for both skill sets to cultivate well-rounded graduates (de Villiers, 2010; Howieson et al., 2014). A significant challenge, however, is the scarcity of research dedicated to evaluating these non-technical skills (Bayerlein & Timpson, 2017). Given that assessment methods heavily direct student learning in formal education (Boud & Falchikov, 2006) it is concerning that the approach to lifelong professional competency training seems underdeveloped, with scholars pointing to a clear lag in innovative assessment for professional development (Gray, 2010; Salem, 2013). If these crucial soft skills are not evaluated effectively, they risk being marginalised in the curriculum, as educational programmes inevitably prioritise what is formally measured (Crowe et al., 2008; Gammie & Joyce, 2009).

A core responsibility for HEIs is curriculum development, which includes the critical task of selecting effective tools to evaluate student competencies. This process often results in the creation of specialised assessment instruments, designed collaboratively by the profession and academic staff, to ensure a curriculum is both high-quality and reliable (White et al., 2016). The creation of such robust competency assessments is fundamental to the formation of a professional identity, and their consistent application helps sustain effective professional performance over time (Bebeau & Monson, 2012; McKee & Eraut, 2012). The relevance and effectiveness of any curriculum are heavily dependent on the quality and precision of its assessment measures, a point strongly emphasised by Wimmers and Mentkowski (2016). Echoing this, Watty et al. (2014) contend that educational quality is demonstrated through the clear alignment of programme and module objectives. They further assert that well-defined learning outcomes must be directly connected to specific learning standards and activities, a process that ultimately produces assessments which are both valid and reliable.

Authentic competency assessment is the cornerstone of meaningful feedback in the teaching and learning process (Alverno College Faculty, 2015). A study at the Alverno College School of Nursing, which employed professional portfolios and interviews, demonstrated the value of evaluating student competence in practical and educational settings. A community of nursing assessors provided observations and judgements on these materials, finding that the process helped candidates gain confidence in articulating their expertise. Each assessment method independently provided critical data for reviewing and refining the curriculum (Alverno College, 2000; O'Brien et al., 2019). Similarly, a study from the Alverno College School of Business (2000) used externally assessed professional interviews and business plans to evaluate competence. The success of some students in business plan competitions underscored the importance of assessing professionalism, interpersonal communication, and general business knowledge. Despite these promising findings, a research gap remains regarding the effectiveness of such methods for developing and evaluating the specific non-technical skills vital to accounting education and professional practice.

Furthermore, while Bloom's Taxonomy is widely used in education, its specific application within accounting and finance remains under-explored. Existing research points to a significant

disconnect between academic accounting instruction and the demands of professional practice, underscoring the urgency of enhancing and evaluating soft skills. A critical barrier is the lack of suitable assessment tools to promote deep, lasting learning in these areas. Consequently, the research gap identified is the need for a contextualised framework, based on Bloom's Taxonomy, to analyse and evaluate non-technical skills assessment within South African accounting programmes. Such a framework would guide universities in assessing soft skills at different academic levels and support the development and deployment of appropriate assessment instruments.

SAICA'S CA2025 CF Key Competencies

In the South African context, a SAICA accreditation serves as a benchmark for teaching quality, underscoring the requirement for graduates to demonstrate both technical mastery and a well-developed set of professional competencies. These essential competencies include digital fluency, sound professional ethics, and strong business, decision-making, and relational acumen (Landsdell et al., 2020). The SAICA CA2025 Competency Framework formally delineates the core technical, ethical, and digital proficiencies for aspiring Chartered Accountants, with a dedicated focus on cultivating these vital soft skills (Nomlala & Mvunabandi, 2023). The Framework particularly emphasises the growing importance of business, decision-making, relational, and digital acumen in the modern workplace (Landsberg & van den Berg, 2023). By explicitly integrating these soft skills, the CA2025 CF acknowledges the comprehensive nature of the chartered accountant's role, which demands that technical expertise be complemented by strategic and interpersonal capabilities. This reflects SAICA's dedication to developing adaptable professionals who are not only technically adept but also excel in communication, ethical judgement, and leadership (Landsdell et al., 2020).

Decision-making and relational acumen encompass a broad suite of soft skills, such as communication, critical and integrated thinking, problem-solving, leadership, and emotional intelligence, alongside the ability to build relationships, work in teams, and maintain professional scepticism (Parsons et al., 2020).

The explicit inclusion of these competencies in the SAICA CA2025 Competency Framework is designed to ensure that future Chartered Accountants are equipped to handle the profession's complex demands and make meaningful contributions to their organisations and communities. According to Parsons, Davidowitz, and Maughan (2020), it is precisely these soft skills, over and above technical and digital expertise, that distinguish a professional's competency and enable them to excel in a dynamic field. Research by Plant, Barac, and Sarens (2019) further confirms that soft skills are fundamental in shaping socially responsible professionals prepared for a variety of roles. Consequently, the effective evaluation of these skills in trainee accountants is critical; it directly impacts the relevance of accounting education and ensures that new graduates can immediately contribute to organisational success.

Globally, the methods for developing and assessing these skills vary significantly between developed and emerging economies. Studies note that these differences are shaped by divergent educational systems, available resources, and cultural contexts (Gammie, Cargill, & Hamilton, 2010; Cimatti, 2016). In countries like the United States and the United Kingdom, soft skills are often systematically woven into the educational fabric from an early age

through to higher education, using methods such as group projects, debates, and structured internships (Jackson & Meek, 2021). In contrast, the South African approach involves a blend of traditional academic assessments, professional body requirements such as the SAICA examinations and workplace-based evaluations, including appraisals and continuing professional development (Plant et al., 2019; Lansdell et al., 2020). A persistent challenge within the local context, however, is that a frequent lack of resources constrains the consistent and effective development and assessment of these vital skills. While SAICA exerts a significant influence on accounting education, the ultimate responsibility for designing curricula and assessments rests with individual universities. These institutions must align their programmes either with the SAICA CF or with the Higher Education Qualifications Sub-Framework (HEQSF) standards tied to the National Qualifications Framework (NQF) pathways (Terblanche & De Clercq, 2021). Consequently, although the SAICA framework offers a clear set of guidelines, each university retains the autonomy to decide how these are practically integrated into their specific accounting programmes.

The fundamental objective in crafting an accounting curriculum, irrespective of whether it follows NQF levels or the SAICA framework, is not to attain flawless learning outcomes. Rather, the goal is to ensure that assessment methods accurately measure the competencies outlined in those outcomes (Parsons et al., 2020). It is therefore imperative for universities to meticulously construct their accounting curricula and evaluations. This design must not only comply with the relevant standards but must also address the needs of their student body and effectively equip them for the rigours of the professional accounting environment.

Method

This study employs a non-systematic literature review, utilising a qualitative document analysis approach guided by a rigorous process to uphold validity and reliability. The research focuses on a defined corpus of published, peer-reviewed journal articles in English that investigate the assessment of soft skills or topics related to the 4IR. From this body of literature, a final sample of 14 articles was selected for in-depth analysis based on their direct relevance to the study's aims, as outlined in Table 1.

Table 1

Sampled Studies

	Title of article	Author (s)	Date Published	Grouping	Name of Peer-reviewed journal
1	Reimagining curricula for the Fourth Industrial Revolution	Menon & Castrillón	2019	4IR	The Independent Journal of Teaching and Learning
2	Skills, competencies, and literacies attributed to 4IR/Industry 4.0: Scoping review	Chaka	2020	4IR	IFLA Journal
3	Critical soft skills for information and knowledge management practitioners in the fourth industrial revolution	Mabe & Bwalya	2022	4IR	South African Journal of Information Management
4	Bridging the employability skills gap: going beyond classroom Walls	Tan, Laswad, & Chua,	2022	Soft skills	Pacific Accounting Review
5	Exploring Relevant Employability Skills 4.0 For University Students' Readiness in The Work-Based Learning Program	Halili, Fathima & Razak,	2022	4IR	Journal of Technical Education and Training
6	Positioning African women for the fourth industrial revolution (4IR) era: Insights for women students	Potokri,	2022	4IR	Prizren Social Science journal
7	4th Industrial Revolution skills in the current South African accountancy curricula: A systematic literature review	Landsberg & van den Berg's	2023	4IR/soft skills	South African Journal of Accounting Research
8	University accounting programmes and the development of Industry 4.0 soft skills	Lansdell, Moham madali-Haji & Marx,	2020	4IR/soft skills	Journal of Economic and Financial Sciences
9	Developing professional competence in accounting graduates: An action research study	Parsons, Davidowitz, & Maughan,	2020	Soft skills	South African Journal of Accounting Research
10	Preparing work-ready graduates-skills development lessons learnt from internal audit practice	Plant, Barac, & Sarens	2019	Soft skills	Journal of Accounting Education
11	The soft skills of accounting graduates: perceptions versus expectations	Dolce, Emanuel, Cisi & Ghislieri,	2020	Soft skills	Accounting Education
12	Generic skill profiles of future accountants and auditors - Moving beyond attributes	Barac, Plant, Kunz & Kirstein,	2021	Soft skills	Higher Education, Skills and Work-Based Learning
13	Program renewal: students' perception on changes to Teaching pedagogy in auditing	Sexton & Rudman,	2022	Soft skills	South African Journal of Higher Education
14	Relational and decision-making skills development in South African accounting students	Kotze & Miller	2023	Soft skills	Industry and Higher Education

Notably, most of the articles were published within the last few years (2019-2023), ensuring that the research is built on the latest understandings and developments in the field. This is particularly fundamental when studying rapidly evolving topics like the 4IR.

This is enlightened by the fact that the articles were derived from various peer-reviewed journals, demonstrating an international view on the issues related to 4IR and soft skills. This diversity in sources adds to the validity and global applicability of the research.

The chosen journals in Table 1, such as The Independent Journal of Teaching and Learning, IFLA Journal, and Journal of Economic and Financial Sciences, are reputable and peer-reviewed, ensuring the academic credibility and quality of the research presented in the articles. Within this, the selected articles include in-depth explorations, such as systematic literature reviews, scoping reviews, and action research studies. This variety in research methodologies provides a holistic view of the subject matter and allows for a more nuanced analysis in the research paper. In this vein, some articles focus on the practical application of skills in specific industries, such as accounting auditing. This industry-specific focus adds depth to the research, making it applicable to real-world scenarios and addressing the needs of professions.

Results

The results are categorized into two themes: studies concentrating on 4IR and those delving into soft skills and their evaluation in accounting education. The findings underscore a discernible need for a comprehensive framework that integrates perspectives on 4IR, soft skills, and assessment methods within accounting education. In the South African context, the SAICA CF serves as a benchmark for evaluating the requisite soft skills.

The 4IR Skills

This literature suggests that there are specific skills and competencies needed to help graduates function effectively in industry within the era of 4IR. Hence, there is a consensus about this within the literature, and yet, there is little attention on the methods that should be used by universities to assess these skills. Table 2 provides insights from various studies on the integration of 4IR concepts into education, particularly accounting. It highlights findings such as the importance of soft skills, discrepancies in curricula alignment, and the need for innovative approaches to bridge the gap between education and industry demands.

Table 2

Summary of Studies on the Integration of 4IR Concepts into Accounting Education

Author	Date	Title	Objective	Type of study	Key Findings
Menon & Castrillón	2019	Reimagining curricula for the Fourth Industrial Revolution	Looks into the context in which programmes are designed and approved in South Africa.	Conceptual Paper	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • New approaches to curricula and programme types are essential within the context of 4IR. • Current focus is on predefined categories and types of learning. • Changes in teaching technologies and tools have not been matched by flexibility in policies and processes
Chaka	2020	Skills, competencies, and literacies attributed to 4IR/Industry 4.0: Scoping review	To identify skills, competencies and literacies attributed to the fourth industrial revolution	Literature Review (64 peer reviewed articles)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Skills and competencies attributed to 4IR by 54 of the 64 reviewed journal articles were generic soft skills (e.g. communication, innovation, creativity, problem solving etc.). • Hard skills such as programming skills also featured in the articles reviewed. • Information literacy in under-represented and under-cited as a skill for 4IR
Mabe & Bwalya	2022	Critical soft skills for information and knowledge management practitioners in the fourth industrial revolution	To determine the soft skills IKM (Information and Knowledge Management) practitioners require in the 4IR, particularly in South Africa.	Systematic and targeted literature review	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Soft skills have surpassed hard skills in importance and success. • 57 skills were identified, but only 17 had consensus with experts
Tan, Laswad, & Chua,	2022	Bridging the employability skills gap: going beyond classroom walls	To explore the impact of two types of ELAs out-of-class experience in the development of employability skills from the accounting students' perspective	Primary research	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The results show that extracurricular activities can help accounting students develop a wide range of skills • Accounting students' reflections of their experiences indicated that their involvement fosters cognitive and behavioural skills development.

Halili, Fathima & Razak,	2022	Exploring Relevant Employability Skills 4.0 For University Students' Readiness in The Work-Based Learning Program	To identify the relevant employability skills in relation to the student's readiness for employability 4.0 in a work-based learning program.	Primary research	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> found six employability skills relevant to the student's readiness for employability 4.0 in the WBL program ((i) communication (COM), (ii) Interpersonal skills (IS), (iii) information technology skills (ITS), (iv) Problem-solving skills (PSS), (v) Entrepreneur skills (EN), (vi) Self-management (SM). skills that directly contribute to the readiness for employability 4.0 in WBL are interpersonal skills (IS), Information technology skills (ITS), problem-solving skills (PSS), entrepreneur skills (EN), and self-management (SM).
Potokri,	2022	Positioning African women for the fourth industrial revolution (4IR) era: Insights for women students	To determine how women can be equipped for relevance for the 4IR era specifically to avoid them been left behind or deepen inequality	Conceptual paper	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> empowerment of women is exposed as the main vehicle for positioning women for relevance in the 4IR era.
Landsberg & van den Berg's	2023	4th Industrial Revolution skills in the current South African accountancy curricula: A systematic literature review	The purpose of the study was to evaluate the alignment between the skills included in the 2025CF and the accountancy curricula of South African universities.	Systematic literature review	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Whilst universities addressed business acumen skills, other skills such as digital, relational, and decision-making skills were inadequately addressed within the curricula of top 5 South African Universities.

The studies, as illustrated in Table 2, collectively emphasise the need for a paradigm shift in curricula, focusing on both hard and soft skills in the 4IR era. Whilst there is a consensus on the importance of generic soft skills, there is an acknowledgement that specific skills may vary depending on different demographic, and socio-cultural factors. For instance, the studies amplify the importance of addressing gender disparities and ensuring alignment between academic curricula and industry demands. What emerges out of these studies are valuable insights into preparing individuals, particularly in the South African context, for the challenges and opportunities presented by the 4IR.

Menon and Castrillón (2019) work is a conceptual paper and lacks empirical evidence and specific details on the assessment methods employed to validate the proposed new approaches. The gap in concrete assessment strategies and their effectiveness limits the applicability and reliability of the suggested curricular changes. On the other hand, Potokri (2022) presents a conceptual paper, and it lacks empirical evidence on how women's empowerment for 4IR is measured or assessed. The absence of precise assessment methods undermines the practicality and reliability of the proposed strategies for women's empowerment.

While the literature review by Chaka (2020) identifies skills for 4IR, it does not delve into the assessment methods used by the studies reviewed. This raises questions about the validity and reliability of the findings, hindering the establishment of a robust skills framework. Similarly, Mabe and Bwalya (2022) systematic literature review identifies soft skills. Still, the lack of detailed information on the assessment methodologies employed by the studies reviewed creates uncertainty about the rigour and

consistency of the identified skills. The absence of a standardised assessment approach hampers the reliability of the findings. On the other hand, Landsberg and van den Berg (2023) conducted a systematic literature review and identified a misalignment in curricula but did not provide insights into the specific assessment methods used by the universities. Without this information, it is challenging to gauge the effectiveness of the assessment practices and their impact on skills development.

Although primary research was conducted, by Tan et al. (2022) their study lacks explicit details on the assessment methods employed to measure the impact of extracurricular activities on skills development. This absence hinders the understanding of the validity and generalizability of the reported results. Whilst Halili et al. (2022) propose the relevance of specific skills for employability 4.0, they do not offer clarity on how these skills were assessed, nor the effectiveness of their assessment methods. Hence, there is an absence of explicit information on assessment methods and their effectiveness, and it limits the reliability of the identified skills and their applicability.

The common thread across these studies is the insufficient attention to detailing the assessment methods used to measure soft skills in the context of the 4IR. The absence of explicit information on assessment strategies and their effectiveness poses a fundamental challenge to the validity, reliability, and comparability of the findings. To enhance the credibility of research in this domain, there is a need to prioritise transparency in reporting assessment methodologies and their effectiveness, thereby allowing for a more robust understanding of the development and evaluation of soft skills in the era of 4IR.

Soft Skills and their Assessments

The benchmark for excellence in university accounting teaching in South Africa is SAICA accreditation, which highlights the critical importance of graduates mastering a blend of technical knowledge, ethical practice, digital tools, and indispensable soft skills (Lansdell et al., 2020). Directly supporting this, the CA2025 Competency

Framework lays out the central proficiencies for Chartered Accountants and places a strong emphasis on the integration of these soft skills (Nomlana & Mvunabandi, 2023). This reflects SAICA's commitment to producing well-rounded professionals, acknowledging the holistic nature of the role (Landsberg & van den Berg, 2023; Lansdell et al., 2020). Studies found in this area are as illustrated in Table 3.

Table 3

Selected Studies Focusing on Assessing Soft Skills

Author	Date	Title	Objective	Type of study	Key Findings
Lansdell, Mohamm adali-haji & Marx,	2020	University accounting programmes and the development of Industry 4.0 soft skills	To elicit the perceptions of entry-level chartered accountants in South Africa (CAs [SA]) on the development of soft skills during a university accounting programme, specifically those soft skills demanded by Industry 4.0	Primary research	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> the accounting programme in question was perceived to have developed most of the soft skills required by Industry 4.0. the development of their creativity and emotional intelligence was lacking
Parsons, Davidowitz, & Maughan,	2020	Developing professional competence in accounting graduates: An action research study	to identify themes in programme design that inform the effective development of professional competence.	Primary research	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> assessment continued to drive learning, while 'value adding' material made little positive contribution. Skills development was found to be more effective when it was explicit. Individual feedback, groupwork and mentorship contributed positively to the development of professional competence, while the contribution of lectures was less clear. large class sizes presented practical challenges to the implementation of effective learning tools.
Plant, Barac, & Sarens	2019	Preparing work-ready graduates-skills development lessons learnt from internal audit practice	Investigated soft skills development as part of continuing professional education (CPE) for early career internal auditors.	Primary research (65 participants)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> adaptability, communication, critical thinking, time management, self-management and teamwork skills are needed to alleviate pressures relating to these challenges
Dolce, Emanuel, Cisi & Ghislieri,	2020	The soft skills of accounting graduates: perceptions versus expectations	to better understand if there is a right match between graduates' perceptions and companies' expectations of the skills that are needed.	Primary research	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Graduates attributed a higher level of importance to the following macroareas of skills: task orientation, motivation, self-awareness, valorisation, and interpersonal relationships. Graduates, compared to companies, underestimated the importance of other soft skills and one specific technical skill, and overestimated other technical skills.
Barac, Plant, Kunz & Kirstein,	2021	Generic skill profiles of future accountants and auditors Moving beyond attributes	To investigate Primary research regarding generic skills future entry-level accountants and auditors will require	Primary research	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Four generic skills factors emerged as essential for future entry-level chartered accountants (CAs): digital, decision-making, organisational and business acumens. Three generic skill factors emerged for future registered auditors (RAs): digital, practice, and commercial acumens.
Sexton & Rudman,	2022	Program renewal: students perception on	to investigate and analyse accounting student	Primary research	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> results indicate that interventions supported the students' deeper learning,

		changes to Teaching pedagogy in auditing	perceptions about the appropriateness of the learning interventions implemented in an accounting programme to focus areas in SAICA's competency framework		engaged in all elements of the learning cycle, was beneficial, <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • students engaged in meaningful learning of technical skills, as well as developing professional skills and competencies.
Kotze & Miller	2023	Relational and (RDM) skills development in South African accounting students	How can the academic programme better prepare CA (sa) students for the training programme, specifically with regard to relational and decision-making skills?	Primary research (44 aspirant chartered accountants in South Africa)	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • All RDM skills are developed to an intermediate or advanced level during the academic programme. • The academic programme should develop all RDM skills (e.g. teamwork, relationship-building, leadership etc.)

The studies collectively underscore the importance of a well-rounded approach to skills development, aligning with SAICA's competencies. They highlight the need for a balance between technical and soft skills, the importance of continuous education, and the influence of program design and class sizes on skills development. The divergence between graduate perceptions and industry expectations emphasizes the ongoing challenge of preparing accounting professionals with the necessary competencies. For instance, Lansdell et al. (2020) study relies on perceptions, possibly subject to self-reporting bias. The lack of specific assessment methods challenges the reliability of claims about the development of soft skills in accounting programs. While Plant et al. (2019) identified crucial soft skills, the assessment methods for determining the level of these skills remain unclear. The absence of a detailed examination of assessment strategies limits insights into their effectiveness. In a similar vein, Barac et al. (2021) identify generic skills factors but do not delve into the specific assessment methods employed to evaluate these skills. Without such information, it is challenging to ascertain the validity and reliability of the findings. Parsons et al. (2020). draw attention to assessment as a driver for learning, and this raises concerns about the true efficacy of the learning process. Lack of clarity on how assessments are designed and implemented impedes a nuanced understanding of their impact on skills development. Similarly, Dolce et al. (2020) reveal a disparity between graduate perceptions and industry expectations. However, there is a lack of an in-depth examination of the assessment methods used to measure these soft skills, leaving ambiguity about the criteria and tools employed.

Sexton and Rudman (2022) draw attention to the positive impact of interventions, but the study does not provide a thorough exploration of the assessment methods used to measure the effectiveness of these interventions. This limits the understanding of how assessments contribute to skills development. While Kotze and Miller (2023) make claims about the development of relational and decision-making skills, their study lacks transparency on the assessment tools or criteria used. Without this information, it is difficult to gauge the rigour of the assessment process. The studies collectively lack detailed insights into the assessment methods employed to measure or assess soft skills. There is a pervasive need for transparency regarding the design, implementation, and evaluation of assessments in accounting programs. The absence of a standardized approach to assess soft skills raises concerns about the

reliability, validity, and comparability of findings across studies. Additionally, the reliance on self-reported perceptions without concrete evidence from assessment methods challenges the credibility of claims about the effectiveness of accounting programs in developing industry-relevant soft skills. Hence, there is a need to address these methodological gaps to enhance the robustness of findings in the field of accounting education. These findings reveal that there is a need for some guidelines that help to integrate perspectives of 4IR, soft skills, and assessment methods in accounting education. Here, the SAICA CF is used as a measure of the soft skills required. Whilst studies highlight assessment methods used to measure soft skills, there is still need for a standardised approach to assess soft skills within the South African context of accounting education.

Discussion

The discussion of this non-systematic qualitative review results reveals a critical paradox within South African accounting education. While there is a clear and urgent consensus on the importance of soft skills for navigating the (4IR) (Chaka, 2020; Mabe & Bwalya, 2022) the methods for assessing these competencies remain opaque, inconsistent, and insufficiently detailed in the literature. This discussion synthesises the findings from the two emergent themes which are 4IR competencies and soft skills assessment to argue that the absence of a standardised and transparent framework for evaluating soft skills undermines the strategic intent of the SAICA CA2025 CF and jeopardises the work-readiness of accounting graduates.

The first key finding is that studies focusing on the 4IR, while valuable in identifying essential skills, consistently lack granularity regarding their assessment. For instance, the conceptual work of Menon and Castrillón (2019) and Potokri (2022) calls for curricular transformation but fails to propose concrete, empirically tested assessment strategies. Similarly, literature reviews by Chaka (2020) and Mabe and Bwalya (2022) successfully catalogue the generic soft skills demanded by the 4IR such as problem-solving, innovation, and interpersonal skills yet offer no insight into how these skills are or should be measured. This omission is significant, as Landsberg and van den Berg (2023) systematically identified that these very skills: digital, relational, and decision-making acumen are the ones most under-addressed in current South African accountancy curricula. The primary research of Tan et al. (2022) and Halili et al.

(2022) demonstrates that skills can be developed through extracurricular and work-based learning; however, without explicit details on the assessment methods used to measure this development, the validity and reliability of their findings are difficult to ascertain. This collective failure to prioritise and detail assessment methodology creates a substantial gap between identifying necessary skills and proving they have been effectively cultivated.

This assessment gap is further exacerbated within the specific context of SAICA-accredited accounting programmes. The second key finding demonstrates that even studies directly investigating soft skills in accounting education suffer from a lack of methodological transparency. For example, Lansdell et al. (2020) rely on self-reported perceptions of skills development, a method vulnerable to bias, without corroborating these perceptions with objective assessment data. Studies by Plant et al. (2019) and Barac et al. (2021) identify crucial soft skills profiles but do not elucidate the assessment tools used to evaluate them. This pattern persists in action research; Parsons et al. (2020) rightly identify assessment as a key driver of learning, yet the specific design and implementation of their assessments remain unclear, making it challenging for other institutions to replicate their approach. The consequence, as highlighted by Dolce et al. (2020) is a persistent misalignment between graduate self-perceptions and employer expectations which is a disconnect that likely stems from inadequate or poorly aligned assessment practices.

The findings collectively underscore a pervasive issue: if soft skills are not robustly assessed, they risk being marginalised in the curriculum, as students and educators inevitably prioritise what is formally measured (Boud & Falchikov, 2006; Gammie & Joyce, 2009). The SAICA CA2025 CF provides an excellent blueprint for what the essential competencies for a future Chartered Accountant (SAICA, 2022). However, this study reveals a critical deficiency in the how the practical mechanisms for evaluating these competencies in a valid, reliable, and standardised manner across South African

HEIs. The proposed framework of eight propositions, situated at the intersection of 4IR demands and the SAICA framework, directly addresses this deficiency. It moves the discourse from simply identifying skills to operationalising their assessment through a multi-dimensional approach that emphasises contextual alignment, validity, reliability, and continuous improvement.

The propositions for a multi-dimensional assessment approach incorporating self, peer, and expert evaluation are supported by broader educational research advocating for such methods to capture the complexity of professional competencies (Wimmers & Mentkowski, 2016). Furthermore, the call for integrating technology into assessment design is not merely about digital proficiency but about creating authentic scenarios that mirror the technology-saturated, collaborative environments of the modern workplace (Tsiligiris & Bowyer, 2021). By advocating for transparency in assessment methodology and a standardised approach guided by the propositions, this study provides a pathway to enhance the credibility of accounting programmes, ensure graduates possess the holistic acumen required by the profession, and ultimately bridge the troubling gap between education and industry expectations in South Africa.

Propositions for Assessing Soft Skills in Accounting Education

The findings reveal that the landscape of accounting education is continually evolving, driven by technological advancements, globalization, and the dynamic demands of the 4IR (Menon & Castrillón, 2019; Chaka, 2020; Mabe & Bwalya, 2022). Scholars suggest that, in this context, assessing and developing soft skills is crucial for producing well-rounded professionals who can thrive in the complex and rapidly changing business environment (Plant et al., 2019; Lansdell et al., 2020; Kotze & Miller, 2023). Drawing from the findings, the study makes 8 propositions for soft skills assessments within the context of South African accounting education as illustrated in Table 4.

Table 4

Propositions for Soft Skills Assessment

Propositions for Soft Skills Assessment			
	Assessment Adaptations	Actions for Soft skills Assessments	
Propositions	Contextual Alignment	SAICA Competency Framework Alignment Identify and align soft skills assessment methods with the relevant competencies outlined in the SAICA Competency Framework.	
	Assessment Design	Address needs and demands of 4IR	Ensure that the assessment addresses the specific needs and demands of the 4IR, such as adaptability, critical thinking, and technological proficiency.
		Multi-dimensional Approach	Employ a mix of assessment methods to capture a comprehensive view of soft skills. Include self-assessment, peer assessments, and expert evaluations to provide diverse perspectives.
		Technology Integration	Leverage digital platforms and tools to assess soft skills related to technological literacy, collaboration in virtual environments, and adaptability to technological changes.
	Validity and Reliability	Content Validity	Ensure that assessment content is directly related to the soft skills required in the 4IR and SAICA Competency Framework.
		Reliability	Conduct pilot testing to ensure consistent and reliable results across different assessors and contexts.
	Feedback and Development	Feedback and Development	Provide detailed feedback to individuals on their soft skills performance, highlighting strengths and areas for improvement.
		Developmental Plans	Facilitate the creation of personalized development plans based on assessment results, linking them to relevant training and resources.
Ethical	Fairness and	Ensure that assessment methods are fair and inclusive, considering diverse	

		Considerations Inclusivity backgrounds and experiences.
	Privacy and Data Security	Implement robust measures to protect the privacy and security of assessment data, especially in the digital realm.
Continuous Improvement	Feedback Loop	Establish a continuous feedback loop involving participants, assessors, and stakeholders to refine the assessment process over time.
	Adaptation to Technological Advances	Stay updated with technological trends and update assessment methods accordingly to ensure relevance.
Integration with Learning and Development Programs	Alignment with Training Programs	Integrate soft skills assessment results with ongoing learning and development initiatives.
Benchmarking	Reflective Practice	Encourage individuals to reflect on their soft skills development and apply feedback in real-world scenarios
	External Benchmarking	Compare soft skills assessment results with industry benchmarks to gauge the effectiveness of the assessment methods.
	Longitudinal Analysis	Conduct longitudinal analyses to track the progression of soft skills development over time.

Therefore, this study makes contributions by making some proposals to enhance the effectiveness of soft skills assessment in preparing accountants for the challenges of the future. The proposals are organised into 8 propositions that are located at the intersection of 4IR and the need to assess soft skills within the context of South African accounting education. These are focused on Contextual Alignment, Assessment Design, Validity and Reliability, Feedback and Development, Ethical Considerations, and Continuous Improvement. These propositions are rooted in a comprehensive review of prior research located within both the 4IR literature (refer to Table 2) and soft skills assessment literature (refer to Table 3). Immersed in academic discourse, the researchers gleaned valuable insights informing the development of these propositions.

Proposition 1: Contextual Alignment

Aligning soft skills assessments with the SAICA CF is essential for ensuring that accounting education meets industry standards. By identifying and integrating relevant competencies outlined in the framework, educators can tailor assessments to address the specific needs and demands of the accounting profession. This alignment provides a foundation for developing skills such as adaptability, critical thinking, and technological proficiency, which are vital in navigating the complexities of the 4IR.

Proposition 2: Assessment Design

A multi-dimensional approach to assessment design is crucial for capturing a comprehensive view of soft skills. Incorporating self-assessment, peer assessments, and expert evaluations provides diverse perspectives, allowing for a more accurate evaluation of an individual's abilities. Moreover, leveraging digital platforms for assessment purposes enables the evaluation of technological literacy, collaboration in virtual environments, and adaptability to technological changes, aligning with the demands of the 4IR.

Proposition 3: Validity and Reliability

Ensuring the content validity of assessments is paramount to their effectiveness. The content must directly relate to the soft skills required in the 4IR and SAICA CF. Conducting pilot testing is

essential to establish the reliability of assessment results across different assessors and contexts, ensuring consistent and dependable outcomes.

Proposition 4: Feedback and Development

Providing detailed feedback to individuals based on their soft skills performance is a key element in fostering development. Highlighting strengths and areas for improvement allows individuals to understand their capabilities better and take targeted actions for growth. Facilitating the creation of personalized development plans linked to relevant training and resources further supports individuals in their continuous improvement journey.

Proposition 5: Ethical Considerations

Ethical considerations play a vital role in the design and implementation of soft skills assessments. Ensuring fairness and inclusivity is crucial, considering diverse backgrounds and experiences. Implementing robust measures for privacy and data security becomes imperative, particularly in the digital realm, to protect sensitive assessment data and maintain the trust of participants.

Proposition 6: Continuous Improvement

Establishing a feedback loop involving participants, assessors, and stakeholders contributes to continuous improvement. Regularly refining the assessment process based on feedback ensures its relevance and effectiveness over time. Staying updated with technological trends and adapting assessment methods accordingly is essential to keep pace with the evolving demands of the accounting profession.

Proposition 7: Integration with Learning and Development Programs

Integrating soft skills assessment results with ongoing learning and development initiatives enhances the practical applicability of the acquired skills. Reflective practice, encouraging individuals to apply feedback in real-world scenarios, ensures that the soft skills developed are not only theoretical but also applicable in professional settings.

Proposition 8: Benchmarking

External benchmarking against industry standards allows educators to gauge the effectiveness of soft skills assessment methods. Comparing results with established benchmarks provides insights into areas of improvement and aligns educational practices with industry expectations. Additionally, conducting longitudinal analyses to track the progression of soft skills development over time contributes valuable data for refining educational strategies.

Conclusion

In conclusion, this paper has sought to meticulously investigate the incorporation and congruence of 4IR concepts within the documented methodologies employed by South African Higher Education Institutions (HEIs) for cultivating and evaluating soft skills within SAICA-accredited programs. In the studies reviewed, there is evidence of insufficient attention to detailing soft skills assessment methods in Fourth Industrial Revolution studies. This undermines validity, reliability, and comparability. Therefore, prioritizing transparency in reporting methodologies is crucial for enhancing credibility, ensuring a robust understanding of soft skills development and evaluation in the 4IR era. It also emerged that the studies reviewed lacked detailed insights into soft skills assessment methods in accounting programs. As such, a pervasive need for transparency in design, implementation, and evaluation raises concerns about reliability, validity, and comparability. Addressing these gaps is crucial for enhancing the robustness of findings in accounting education.

It is concluded that the integration of soft skills assessments into accounting education is essential for preparing professionals for the challenges posed by the 4IR. The propositions of Assessment Adaptations and Actions for Soft Skills Assessments, including Contextual Alignment, Assessment Design, Validity and Reliability, Feedback and Development, Ethical Considerations, and Continuous Improvement, collectively contribute to the advancement of knowledge in accounting education. Future studies should explore innovative ways to enhance soft skills assessment methodologies, considering emerging technologies, global trends, and industry expectations. By addressing these considerations, accounting education can remain adaptive, relevant, and effective in producing graduates equipped for success in the ever-changing professional landscape.

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Received October 29, 2025

Revision received November 24, 2025

Accepted November 30, 2025